

Recyclable and sustainable packaging solutions in the meat industry: exploring eco-friendly alternatives to plastic

Dushyant Kumar, Shivam Singh Thakur, Nitesh Choudhary, and
Amit Kulhar

Department of Livestock Products Technology
Post Graduate Institute of Veterinary Education and Research, Jaipur
Rajasthan University of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Jobner, Jaipur
Corresponding author email: d.k.jindal721991@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Sustainable meat packaging is gaining momentum as the meat industry seeks alternatives to traditional plastic materials due to environmental concerns. Innovations in biodegradable, compostable, recyclable, and edible packaging are emerging to reduce ecological footprints while maintaining meat quality and safety. Biodegradable materials like polylactic acid (PLA) and polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) offer natural decomposition, whereas recyclable options such as mono-material plastics and fiber-based trays enhance waste management. Edible packaging, derived from biopolymers like chitosan and alginate, provides additional benefits by reducing waste and extending shelf life. Despite these advancements, challenges persist, including higher costs, limited scalability, and regulatory hurdles. Addressing these issues through technological innovation and consumer education is crucial for the widespread adoption of sustainable meat packaging solutions.

KEYWORDS: Sustainable meat packaging, biodegradable materials, compostable films, recyclable packaging, edible packaging

INTRODUCTION

Sustainability in meat packaging is a growing concern due to the environmental impact of traditional plastic-based materials. The development of recyclable and biodegradable alternatives such as bioplastics, compostable films, and fiber-based packaging has gained significant attention. This article explores the latest innovations in sustainable meat packaging, their benefits, and the challenges associated with their adoption. The meat industry relies heavily on plastic packaging due to its barrier properties, durability, and cost-effectiveness (Robertson, 2013). However, concerns over plastic pollution and regulatory pressures have led to a shift towards sustainable packaging solutions (Realini & Marcos, 2014). Sustainable packaging aims to reduce environmental

impact while maintaining meat quality and safety (Kerry *et al.*, 2006).

BIODEGRADABLE AND COMPOSTABLE PACKAGING

Biodegradable packaging is generally defined as any form of packaging that will naturally disintegrate and decompose. Biodegradable materials such as polylactic acid (PLA) and polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA) are emerging as viable alternatives to conventional plastics (Vermeiren *et al.*, 1999). These materials decompose under natural conditions, reducing waste accumulation (Ahvenainen, 2003). Starch-based films and cellulose derivatives offer similar benefits and are already being incorporated into commercial meat packaging (Vargas *et al.*, 2012).